

**make
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Deliverable D1.1 Project Handbook

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Revision of History

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
CCI	Cultural and Creative Industries
CDO	Communication, Dissemination and Outreach
CH	Cultural Heritage
CO	Confidential
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
ECA	European Craft Association
FCF	Sihtasutus Fab City Foundation
FRG	Fashion Revolution Germany
GA	General Assembly
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering e.V.
IAAC	Institut d'Arquitectura Avancada de Catalunya
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
OD	OpenDot SRL
PII	Personal Identifiable Information
PL2030	Public Libraries 2030
PMB	Project Management Board
PU	Public
PU	Public relations
RE	Restricted
RRI	Responsible Research & Innovation
UMA	Ukrainian Makers Association
USP	Unique Selling Proposition
WP	Work Package
WP1	Management 1

WP2	Management 2
WP3	Mapping and Community Activation
WP4	Modular Makerspace Approach
WP5	Capacity Development
WP6	Community Engagement
WP7	European Public Library Pilots
WP8	Exploitation and Sustainability
WP9	CDO1 (Communication, Dissemination & Outreach 1)
WP10	CDO2 (Communication, Dissemination & Outreach 2)
WP11	Impact Assessment
ZSI	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation GmbH

Executive Summary

This Project Handbook outlines the internal procedures of the *make-a-thek* consortium, focusing on management structures, communication and collaboration practices, and quality control measures. It also defines the consortium's approach to **Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)**, with particular attention to ethical considerations around personal data collection, analysis, and storage. These topics will be further detailed in the **Data Management Plan (DMP)** to be delivered in Month 6. Key pillars of the consortium's RRI strategy—**open source** and **open access**—are embedded throughout the project and reflected in both this handbook and the DMP.

The primary audience for this document is the project's consortium partners, as it serves as an internal reference to support high-quality, coordinated research across a diverse set of institutions. It is also intended as a practical guide for any new team members joining the project at a later stage.

Given the diversity of expertise and backgrounds within the consortium, *make-a-thek* is guided by principles of **open participation, flexibility, and transparency**, particularly in regard to project progress and risk identification. These values shape our internal processes and help ensure effective collaboration across a distributed team.

To support smooth operation, clear communication procedures have been established. Regular meetings are held both virtually (via web conferencing) and in person. Ongoing communication is supported through email and a dedicated project mailing list. For collaborative work, **Google Drive** and **Basecamp**¹ are used as the primary platforms, with **Basecamp** serving as the secure environment for sharing any sensitive data. Basecamp is the main access point for collaboration and is interlinked with Google Drive. Also, Basecamp will serve as the collaboration space for the pilot community.

A strong commitment to **quality assurance** underpins the project. All deliverables undergo an internal **peer review** process, guided by established quality standards. To continuously improve internal collaboration, short surveys or reflective sessions may be conducted—typically during project meetings—as tools for group self-assessment and process refinement.

In terms of **ethics**, the consortium adheres to the European Commission's guidelines² and maintains a strong commitment to respecting individual privacy at all times. Templates for informed consent (as outlined in Deliverable D1.2 – Data Management Plan) and for the secure exchange of primary research data—including personal data—have been prepared. All data practices comply with **GDPR** regulations and include provisions for the lawful transfer of data between EU and third countries. The project management also places strong emphasis on

¹ <https://basecamp.com>

² <https://allea.org/code-of-conduct/>

raising awareness of ethical and RRI-related issues throughout the project's lifecycle.

Finally, **openness** is a core value of *make-a-thek*. The project actively explores **open strategies** for its research and innovation outputs—ranging from the release of software under open licences and the adoption of open standards, to the open access publication of research findings wherever possible.

This handbook is conceived as a **living document**. It will be updated as needed to reflect improvements, adapt to new challenges, and further enhance internal coordination and quality throughout the project.

1. Introduction

make-a-thek aims to establish modular, replicable makerspace set-ups within public libraries, offering open access to innovative and circular approaches in fashion and crafts. Grounded in extensive mapping and participatory co-creation, the project will develop a comprehensive resource toolkit and a suite of open educational resources (OERs) tailored for fashion- and craft-focused makerspaces in libraries. These will be piloted in at least nine European and three international library locations.

Throughout these pilot trials, communities of practitioners and prosumers (engaged citizens) will co-design and test new models for integrating traditional heritage crafts with digital fabrication techniques. This process will foster the exchange and development of tools, skills, techniques, and cultural practices that promote circularity in fashion and crafts.

Aligned with the principles of the **New European Bauhaus**³, *make-a-thek* embodies:

- **Inclusivity:** by democratising access to innovation technologies and creating new public infrastructures that invite citizens to actively participate in the green transition,
- **Sustainability:** by empowering communities to contribute to a circular society through creative and practical engagement,
- **Enrichment:** by enabling personal and collective expression through hands-on work in fashion and crafts.

With a strong focus on **social innovation**, the project aims to generate impact across four key dimensions, measured through **Societal Readiness Levels** and aligned with the European Commission’s work programme:

- Empowering New Prosumers in Fashion and Crafts
- Positioning Public Libraries as Inclusive Hubs for Circular Knowledge and Creation
- Preserving Heritage Crafts through Digital Innovation and Skills Development
- Fostering Circularity and Green Innovation in Fashion and Craft Sectors

To ensure sustainability and long-term uptake, *make-a-thek* will pursue a scaling strategy that extends beyond the pilot sites. This includes building a broader network, embedding practices into existing infrastructures, and producing an ***make-a-thek (Scaling) Guide*** targeted at Cultural and Creative Sectors as well as Cultural Heritage stakeholders.

³ <https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/>

1.1 The *make-a-thek* concept

The *make-a-thek* concept (see Picture 1) integrates key considerations into a modular framework that supports the creation of inclusive spaces, strategies, and methodologies for sustainable crafts and fashion. This approach promotes circularity while being firmly rooted in local ecosystems. Modularity is essential, as the concept must be adaptable to diverse and complex cultural contexts in order to scale effectively. Flexibility is a foundational element of the model, enabling tailored implementation across varying environments.

Picture 1: *make-a-thek* concept

Building on the current transformation of public libraries—from traditionally theory-driven institutions into more hands-on, community-oriented spaces—*make-a-thek* recognises three distinct types of public libraries based on their existing levels of expertise in making, crafts, and circularity:

1. **Beginner Level:** Libraries with no existing makerspace and no prior experience in making, crafts, or circularity (e.g. Antwerp Central Library, Belgium).
2. **Intermediate Level:** Libraries that have established makerspaces equipped with digital fabrication technologies and are looking to expand into fashion- and craft-related practices (e.g. Kranj City Library, Slovenia).

3. **Advanced Level:** Libraries with fully operational makerspaces and ongoing programmes in craft and fashion, but without a dedicated focus on circularity—yet showing a strong interest in developing activities and services in this area (e.g. Helsinki Central Library Oodi, Finland).

This tiered model allows *make-a-thek* to support libraries at various stages of development, offering customised pathways for integrating circular practices and strengthening their roles as hubs of sustainable innovation.

1.2 The *make-a-thek* project phases & methodological steps

make-a-thek is structured around three core phases (see Picture 2):

- **Phase 1** focuses on establishing the knowledge and resource foundation necessary for the successful implementation of the pilot trials.
- **Phase 2** involves the rollout of pilot trials across the EU, supported by targeted capacity-building and community engagement activities.
- **Phase 3** builds on the insights gained from the European pilots to inform the implementation of pilot trials in the Global South and vice versa, alongside the further exploitation and scaling of project outcomes.

Picture 2: *make-a-thek* project phases & methodological steps

1.2.1 Phase 1: Mapping and Co-Creating Circular Approaches

The project begins with a comprehensive exploration of the needs, ideas, and existing resources related to circularity in fashion and crafts. This phase involves a thorough needs and resource assessment, engaging diverse stakeholders—including target communities, craftspeople, fashion practitioners, librarians, makers, circularity experts, and the networks represented within the consortium. The goal is to identify existing assets and gaps in infrastructure, knowledge, skills, and resources, while also exploring the potential role of public libraries in advancing circular practices.

Building on existing experiences of libraries with makerspaces, *make-a-thek* will design **modular approaches** tailored for public libraries interested in establishing or expanding makerspace services (WP3).

In *make-a-thek*, **mapping** will be used as a research method to identify how digital technologies are currently applied in circular fashion and crafts, including heritage practices with potential relevance to the fashion industry. This includes baseline desk research and case studies from networks such as Appropedia⁴, Materiom⁵, Hilo Textiles⁶, and Precious Plastic⁷ (WP3).

Alongside mapping, a series of **co-creation events** will be held with target communities to gather insights into digital and maker technologies, sustainable fashion practices, and heritage crafts. Additional research from sources like the Ellen MacArthur Foundation⁸ and Circular.Fashion⁹ will be used to enrich the understanding of future directions for inclusive and sustainable fashion and crafts in Europe.

The process will identify gaps in skills, technology access, materials, and innovation needs. Insights from mapping and co-creation will directly inform the development of resources needed for implementation in Phase 2 (WP3, WP4, WP5).

Key outputs of this phase, which will later be updated in an iterative process, include:

- ***make-a-thek* KIT**: A practical toolkit comprising maker technologies for circularity in fashion and crafts, including open hardware, open designs, fabrication techniques, spatial configurations, and material guidelines for setting up library-based makerspaces. The KIT also introduces methods for digitising heritage crafts, along with viable business models and community engagement strategies (WP4).

⁴ <https://www.appropedia.org/>

⁵ <https://www.materiom.org/>

⁶ <https://www.hilotextiles.com/>

⁷ <https://www.preciousplastic.com/>

⁸ <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/>

⁹ <https://circular.fashion/>

- **make-a-thek OER:** A comprehensive collection of open educational resources developed within the project. This includes the *Skills and Competencies Compass*, *Train-the-Trainer Guides*, and various educational activity manuals, all of which support the launch of makerspace activities during the next phase of piloting (WP5).

This foundational phase, which initiates an iterative approach, sets the stage for successful implementation in the subsequent phases by ensuring that approaches are context-aware, inclusive, and adaptable to diverse library environments.

1.2.2 Phase 2: Piloting, Connecting, and Capacity Building

In Phase 2, *make-a-thek* will launch **11 pilot trials** in public libraries across Europe to test the modular resources developed in Phase 1. Confirmed pilot locations include the following libraries according to WP7:

Country	Location
Slovenia	Kranj
Belgium	Antwerp
Finland	Helsinki
Italy	Milan
Spain	Barcelona
Germany	Berlin
Poland	Opolu
Iceland	Reykjavík
Hungary	Budapest
Ukraine	Kyiv
Ukraine	Zaporizhzhia

Table 1: List of selected pilot trials

Alongside, a **mobile library makerspace** will travel through rural regions across Europe. This mobile tour will reach underrepresented communities—particularly young people—and serve as a **project showcase**, supporting comparative learning across different cultural contexts.

Each participating library will implement selected modules from the *make-a-thek* KIT and engage local communities activated in earlier phases. The pilots aim to explore how public library makerspaces can support **circular practices**—such as repairing, upcycling, and designing fashion—and empower individuals seeking to enhance their creative or entrepreneurial skills.

All pilots will feature:

- **Deep-dive thematic topics**
- **Knowledge exchange and community engagement formats**
- **Training and capacity building for library staff**
- **Peer-review sessions** and **learning events** across pilot sites

Local **stakeholders and communities**—including craftspeople, fashion designers, makers, and digital experts—will collaborate to **digitise heritage crafts** and explore applications of **digital tools**, such as digital twins, to preserve and innovate traditional techniques (WP7 & WP8).

Key Methodologies

- **Co-creation & Prototyping:**
Traditional craft knowledge will be combined with emerging technologies to create new products and services through open innovation and collaborative experimentation hosted in library makerspaces (WP7 & WP8).
- **Peer Learning & Open Educational Resources (OERs):**
High-quality training materials—including design blueprints, tutorials, and how-to guides—will be developed and shared on platforms like Fabricademy¹⁰. These will support both beginners and advanced users, promoting skills in circular design, craft innovation, and entrepreneurship. An "**Adopt, Adapt, Apply**" methodology will guide learners in applying these tools in real-world contexts (WP5).
- **Community Engagement:**
Libraries will strengthen ties with local and international communities, supported by consortium networks such as the Fab City Foundation, Fashion Revolution Germany, Global Innovation Gathering, European Crafts Association, and the Distributed Design Platform coordinated by IAAC. This interconnected ecosystem will foster shared learning, creativity, and long-term impact (WP6, WP7 & WP8).

1.2.3 Phase 3: Sharing, Scaling, and Sustaining

In the final phase, *make-a-thek* focuses on analysing, disseminating, and scaling project results while ensuring long-term sustainability. Key outputs include:

- **Dissemination & Publication** (WP11): Project results will be analysed, documented, and made publicly accessible for further use and replication.

¹⁰ <https://textile-academy.org/>

- **Policy Recommendations** (WP8): Insights from the pilots—particularly on the needs and practices of prosumers in a circular society—will inform policy briefs for both local and EU-level decision-makers.
- **Global Pilot Expansion** (WP7): Building on earlier learnings, at least three pilot trials will be launched in non-EU countries to explore international applicability.
- **Scaling Beyond Libraries** (WP8): The approach will be extended to other cultural and community spaces such as museums, creative hubs, coworking spaces, and community centres, supporting uptake in Cultural and Creative Industries (CCI) and Cultural Heritage (CH) sectors.

Multi-Stakeholder Networking (WP8)

The consortium will host inclusive events—public dialogues, debates, and town-hall meetings—bringing together diverse actors from civil society, government, academia, the private sector, and *make-a-thek*'s target groups. These formats aim to foster cross-sectoral dialogue and shared understanding of the future of circular fashion and craft.

Participatory Evaluation (WP11)

A key feature of this phase is **participatory evaluation**, aligned with the project's co-design philosophy. This bottom-up approach involves stakeholders from the beginning in shaping the evaluation strategy. It emphasises collective reflection, ongoing learning, and adaptive management. Project goals, challenges, success criteria, and unintended outcomes are regularly revisited and assessed collaboratively—making evaluation an integral and transparent part of the project's development and legacy.

1.3 Commitment to Quality, Openness, and Responsible Innovation

The *make-a-thek* project is dedicated to delivering high-quality outcomes through a strong foundation of **responsible research and innovation (RRI)**. This document outlines a set of procedures and guiding principles that the consortium has committed to following—and continuously improving—throughout the project lifecycle.

Openness and transparency are central to the project's ethos, reflected across the methods and processes described in this handbook. At the same time, the consortium places equal importance on **privacy and data protection**, particularly when engaging with individual citizens. These principles align with the broader RRI framework, ensuring that the project's activities are ethically sound, inclusive, and socially responsive.

The remaining parts of this document is structured as follows:

- **Section 2:** Describes the project’s management structures, including appointments to the various governance boards.
- **Section 3:** Outlines specific quality management procedures, including internal communication strategies, peer review processes for deliverables, and tools for risk management such as SWOT analysis.
- **Section 4:** Introduces the technical infrastructure that supports communication and collaboration within the consortium.
- **Section 5:** Details the project’s RRI policies, highlighting important aspects for *make-a-thek*.
- **Section 6:** Explores the project’s commitment to openness, covering both open-source software and open-access publication strategies.
- **Section 7:** Concludes with key reflections and actions needed to ensure the successful, high-quality implementation of the project.

The **appendix** provides templates and examples referenced throughout the document, offering practical tools to support adherence to these shared standards.

2. Management structure

The Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement (CA) define several governance bodies responsible for project management. While these legal documents take precedence over this handbook, the following sections outline how these bodies function from an operational perspective.

make-a-thek is an innovation action, aiming to engage a wide and diverse audience in Europe and beyond. Accordingly, its management structure and procedures are designed to remain flexible, aiming to:

- Ensure the active integration of all consortium members by leveraging their expertise, knowledge, and networks throughout every phase of the project
- Coordinate the implementation of the work plan efficiently within a collaborative setting
- Continuously engage relevant stakeholders and incorporate contextual insights from local pilot sites and community activation initiatives

The management approach blends integration and decentralisation strategies. **Integration** is fostered through the consortium’s complementary expertise, the establishment of a shared framework, alignment on co-design guidelines, collaborative platform and community development, and regular workshops and

meetings. **Decentralisation**, on the other hand, enables effective mobilisation of partner resources by assigning work package leadership and clearly defined tasks according to each partner's area of expertise.

According to the CA the organisational structure of the consortium consists of:

- The **Coordinator** is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority.
- The **Work Package Leaders Group** is an assessment group of the Consortium without formal decision making power. It shall assess the individual and overall implementation of the Project.
- The **General Assembly** is the decision-making body of the consortium.

2.1 Coordinator

The **Coordinator** is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority. ZSI is the official partner representing the coordinator. Dr. Barbara Kieslinger (ZSI), in the role of the project coordinator, oversees the overall management and administrative processes.

The exact responsibilities of the coordinator are outlined in the CA.

GIG, coordinated by Geraldine de Bastion, assumes the second key leadership role, focusing on coordinating the project's knowledge management (Tasks 1.2/2.2). This includes managing interdependencies between work packages and tasks, providing strategic guidance, and ensuring alignment with the project's objectives and long-term sustainability. By leveraging its network and the extensive maker expertise of its members, GIG fosters global knowledge exchange and community development—bringing a vital "Global South" perspective to the *make-a-thek* initiative. GIG also leads efforts related to mapping, community activation, scaling, and sustainability.

The management team of the project is supported in their strategic coordination tasks by the leaders of the respective work packages.

2.2 Work Package Leaders Group

Work packages (WPs) form the fundamental structure of the project. Each WP is led by a designated WP Leader, who is responsible for coordinating activities and ensuring progress within their respective WP. Their key responsibilities include:

- Organizing and overseeing the execution of tasks within the WP
- Preparing and chairing WP meetings
- Managing the production and delivery of WP outputs

- Representing the WP in the Project Management Board

Together, the WP Leaders form the Work Package Leaders Group. It provides both strategic and operational oversight. It ensures that the project remains aligned with its defined and evolving objectives by guiding overall direction and drawing on input from the WP Leaders. The PMB oversees all phases of project management – including initiation, planning, execution, monitoring, and closure.

WP Leaders operate within this framework to coordinate the detailed planning and execution of technical tasks, ensuring progress toward the scientific and technical goals of their respective work packages.

The Group is also responsible for implementing decisions made by the General Assembly and for submitting recommendations on key matters, such as:

- Approving or rejecting changes to the work plan
- Proposing amendments to the Grant Agreement or Consortium Agreement
- Suggesting modifications to the project’s management structure

WP Leaders are supported by task leaders and other consortium members actively involved in the WP. Responsibilities are clearly defined in the WP Description, aligned with each partner’s specific expertise. The current WP leaders are listed in the Table 1 below.

Work Packages	Lead partners	Name of WP Leader
WP1/2 - Project management	ZSI	Barbara Kieslinger
WP3 - Mapping and Community Activation	GIG	Sandra Mamitzsch
WP4 - Modular Makerspace Approach	OD	Cristina Biella
WP5 - Capacity Development	IAAC	Jessica Guy
WP6 - Community Engagement	IAAC	Jessica Guy
WP7 - European Public Library Pilots	PL2030	Ilona Kish
WP8 - Exploitation and Sustainability	GIG	Sandra Mamitzsch
WP9/10 - Communication, Dissemination & Outreach (CDO)	FRG	Hanna Gebauer

WP 11 - Impact Assessment	ZSI	Teresa Schaefer
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Table 2: Assigned WP leaders

2.3 General Assembly (GA)

The General Assembly (GA) is the decision taking body of the project. It consists of one representative of each partner and convenes at least twice a year. Participation in the GA is mandatory for all project partners. The GA serves as a central forum to ensure smooth project implementation, foster integration across work packages, and set the direction for upcoming tasks and activities.

GA meetings are typically held in conjunction with events hosted by consortium members or those closely aligned with the project's objectives.

Key responsibilities of the GA include making decisions on matters such as:

- Amendments to the Description of Action (DoA)
- Financial and budgetary issues
- Intellectual property rights
- Changes to the project consortium (e.g. admission of new partners)
- Major strategic decisions, including potential project termination

Extraordinary GA meetings may be convened at any time upon written request (including email) by any member of the PMB.

2.4 Consortium Agreement (CA)

Prior to the start of the project, all partners signed a Consortium Agreement (CA) outlining the specific operational procedures governing the various project bodies described above. Among other key aspects, the agreement defines the roles and responsibilities of the parties, their mutual liabilities, the governance structure, financial arrangements, and matters related to Intellectual Property Rights (IPR).

The CA also establishes the decision-making framework, designating the GA as the project's highest decision-making authority.

3. Quality Procedures and Code of Conduct

Quality assurance is a key priority in collaborative research initiatives such as *make-a-thek*. The consortium is committed to implementing a comprehensive set of quality management procedures to ensure the production of high-quality project outcomes. These measures include the establishment of structured internal communication channels, systematic risk assessments through regular internal reviews, and the application of a thorough SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis. Furthermore, a clearly defined peer review process will be applied to all project deliverables to safeguard scientific and technical standards.

The specific quality assurance procedures are outlined in detail in the following sections.

3.1 Internal communication structures & procedures

Internal communication within the project is fundamentally guided by the principles of openness and transparency. An active communication strategy has been adopted to foster a strong project identity, ensure maximum clarity for all partners, and enhance collaborative synergy across the consortium.

Day-to-day communication between work packages, partners, and other stakeholders is primarily maintained through the following channels:

- **e-mails** and a central mailing list including all project partners,
- a **WhatsApp** group for quick communication across teams and partners,
- a shared **Google drive** folder for daily collaboration
- a project space - **Basecamp** - hosted at the PL2030 for internal exchange and online storage of all documents that contain any sensitive data (<https://3.basecamp.com/4843423/>)
- web-conferencing (**Zoom**) for regular online meetings,
- easily accessible online collaboration tools, such as **Miroboard, Jamboard**, etc.
- face-to-face communication (during physical project meetings).

Consortium partners meet in person approximately every six to seven months at designated synchronisation points to review and coordinate project progress. In addition, virtual consortium meetings are held at least once a month via web conferencing (e.g., Zoom). These regular meetings facilitate internal communication, enable coordination among Work Package and thematic leaders, and provide a platform for reporting progress to the wider team.

“Live minutes” are documented during each meeting and made accessible to all partners for later reference. Prior to each meeting, teams provide updates in a shared document, allowing participants to review recent developments in advance. The most pressing topics are then addressed during the meeting. All meeting

minutes, excluding any sensitive information, are stored in a shared online project folder for ongoing access.

In addition to the regular virtual consortium meetings, thematic groups aligned with the Work Packages began forming during the kick-off meeting. These working groups independently organise virtual meetings to advance their specific objectives. As with the consortium meetings, notes and recordings from these sessions are made available via Google Drive. All consortium members are welcome to participate in any of these meetings, fostering openness and cross-collaboration across the project.

3.2 External communication structures & procedures

The communication strategy also focuses on engaging audiences beyond the consortium, which is essential given that *make-a-thek* is an Innovation Action designed to reach a wide audience and generate lasting impact.

Stakeholder engagement will be guided by a comprehensive community engagement and communication strategy, developed collaboratively by WP6 (Community Engagement) and WP10/WP11 (Communication, Dissemination & Outreach 1/2). The specific procedures, tools, and materials for external communication will be jointly defined and harmonised across these work packages. Tailored communication approaches will be developed to effectively reach and engage the various target groups.

3.3 Quality of (non-) deliverables and peer reviews

A **peer-review process** has been established within the *make-a-thek* project to ensure the quality and integrity of all deliverables—such as documentation, reports, and prototypes—produced throughout the project. This process is essential to guarantee that outputs submitted to the European Commission, shared with *make-a-thek* stakeholders, and made available to the broader public meet high standards.

This section outlines the quality standards for *make-a-thek* deliverables and details the peer-review procedure. A deliverable checklist and a peer-review report template are provided in the appendices of this document.

3.3.1 Deliverables

The deliverables produced within the *make-a-thek* project serve multiple functions. They facilitate internal communication among consortium members and act as a key means of sharing information with external stakeholders. Their primary goal is to transfer the knowledge and insights generated by the project, supporting the exploitation of results.

Each deliverable should be crafted with its intended audience in mind, ensuring clarity, conciseness, and ease of understanding. Readability is a critical factor in the effectiveness of any document. To ensure communication is tailored

appropriately, WP10 and WP11 (Communication, Dissemination & Outreach 1/2) support a range of presentation formats suited to different target groups.

According to the Description of Action (DoA), *make-a-thek* deliverables are classified either as “R – Document/Report” or “DEM – Demonstrator, Pilot, Prototype.” Demonstrators often include software prototypes, pilots, or design plans and should be accompanied by a concise supporting report.

Deliverables in report format should follow a standard structure, which is provided in the project’s deliverable template.

- Cover page
- List of Authors/Contributors
- Table of Contents
- Amendment History
- Abbreviations/Acronyms
- Executive summary
- Introductory part
- Core part
- References
- Annexes (optional)

Annex I provides a checklist intended to serve as a guideline for the preparation of project deliverables. A *make-a-thek* deliverable may consist of one or more volumes and typically includes the following components:

- **Main Part:** This section presents a summary of the results, targeting high-level executives, technical managers, and decision-makers. It is usually presented as a single document and may include appendices.
- **Annexes:** These are optional sections containing detailed technical information intended for experts and implementers. Annexes are appended to the main part of the document.

Deliverables are also classified according to confidentiality levels—Public (PU), Restricted (RE), or Confidential (CO). In line with the project's open access strategy, all *make-a-thek* deliverables are designated as Public (PU) in the Description of Action (DoA). This classification allows unrestricted public access, and all deliverables will be made available through the project website and/or open-access platforms such as Zenodo.

Should any consortium member wish to propose a change in the confidentiality level of a deliverable, this must be submitted to the General Assembly for approval, accompanied by a well-justified rationale.

The following outlines the key steps involved in the preparation and submission of a project deliverable:

1. **Foundational Components:** Each deliverable is based on the following elements:
 - Title and description of the deliverable
 - Name(s) of the editor(s) responsible
 - Deliverable history, including the names of contributors and internal reviewers involved in the peer-review process
2. **Initial Contributions:** Authors assigned to specific sections provide their input to the designated editor(s).
3. **Draft Preparation:** The editor compiles and integrates all contributions into an initial version (Draft 0.1). This draft is reviewed in collaboration with the authors. It is recommended to work directly within the shared project drive and involve internal reviewers at this early stage.
4. **First Review-Ready Version:** Once consensus is reached among the editor(s) and authors, the editor prepares Draft 1.0, uploads it to the *make-a-thek* shared drive, and notifies the consortium.
5. **Internal Review:** Internal reviewers are invited to assess the draft, provide feedback, and suggest improvements within a defined timeframe (typically one week).
6. **Revision and Consensus:** The editor addresses all comments and proposed changes, coordinating with authors as needed. This stage may involve multiple interactions and, if necessary, a meeting (in person or virtual) to expedite resolution and consensus on revisions.
7. **Finalization:** The editor finalizes the document (Draft 2.0), uploads it to the shared drive, and informs the Project Manager (Dr. Barbara Kieslinger) and the full consortium that the deliverable is ready for submission.
8. **Submission:** The final version of the deliverable is submitted to the European Commission via the EC portal exclusively by the Project Manager.

3.3.2 Peer review process

An effective way to enhance the quality of project deliverables is through the implementation of an internal peer review system. Each *make-a-thek* deliverable should be evaluated by 2–3 reviewers to ensure a diversity of perspectives and a balanced assessment. Reviewers may include members of the core project team, colleagues from partner institutions, or invited external experts such as members of the Advisory Board.

Peer reviewers should be nominated by the deliverable editor(s) no later than three weeks prior to the deliverable's submission deadline. The nominations must be communicated to the consortium. Reviewers may decline the invitation with a justified reason (e.g., lack of subject-matter expertise or availability) and are encouraged to suggest an alternative candidate.

Once confirmed, reviewers are expected to provide their feedback within 7–10 days of receiving the draft deliverable. Any anticipated delays must be promptly communicated to both the editor and the Project Manager. Throughout the review process, open communication between the reviewers and the main author/editor is encouraged to clarify issues and improve the deliverable.

Peer reviewers are asked to pay particular attention to the following aspects:

- **Alignment with Project Objectives:** Does the deliverable align with the overall goals of the project and the relevant work packages?
- **Contribution to the Project:** Does the deliverable represent a meaningful contribution to the *make-a-thek* project?
- **Focus and Clarity:** Is the content clearly focused on the deliverable's intended purpose? Is the information presented in a clear, concise, and coherent manner?
- **Length and Relevance:** Is the length of the deliverable appropriate for its content? Are there sections that are unnecessary, overly detailed, or off-topic and should be removed or condensed? Are there parts that use overly elaborate language or are vague or repetitive?
- **Language and Style:** Are there grammatical, typographical, or syntactical errors? Are any sentences unclear or difficult to understand? Annotated feedback indicating specific errors and suggested corrections is especially helpful for the authors. The annotated version of the deliverable may be returned to the editor/authors via email along with the peer review report.
- **Need for Revisions:** Does the deliverable require major revisions or rewriting? If so, providing concrete suggestions for improvement will support the revision process and enhance the overall quality of the deliverable.

Peer review outcomes are documented in a peer review report or summary email (refer to the checklist in Annex III), which includes the following elements:

- Basic information on the deliverable, its author(s), and the assigned peer reviewer(s)
- Comments regarding the deliverable's content and length
- Identification of the deliverable's key strengths and weaknesses

- A concise review summary

If the peer review indicates that minor or substantial revisions are required, the editor(s) and author(s) are expected to implement the necessary changes and finalize the deliverable prior to the submission deadline.

While the feedback provided by peer reviewers is intended to support quality improvement, the ultimate responsibility for the content rests with the editor(s) and author(s). They retain full discretion over how reviewer comments are addressed and incorporated.

Peer review reports will be shared internally and made accessible only to consortium members.

Picture 3: Peer review process

3.3.3 Non-deliverables

For non-deliverable outputs—such as publications and dissemination materials—the standard deliverable review procedure will be applied where appropriate, with adjustments made to suit the specific nature and timeline of each item.

Given the wide variety of materials produced, this handbook does not outline procedures for every individual case. However, the following general categories are distinguished:

- **Dissemination Materials** (e.g. flyers, website content, leaflets, popular science articles):

These are primarily reviewed by members of WP10/11 (Communication, Dissemination & Outreach 1/2), with additional support from the project manager.

- **Scientific Publications or Conference Presentations:**

These are reviewed by one or more team members, selected based on their expertise and level of contribution to the specific topic.

3.4 Internal surveys

make-a-thek is committed to a process of continuous improvement at the project management level. In addition to fostering open and transparent communication and decision-making, the project employs anonymous surveys to gather targeted feedback on process management, potential risks, and critical issues. These surveys are intentionally kept concise to encourage participation from all project members.

Surveys are distributed as needed—without a fixed schedule—but are conducted at least once annually, ideally prior to a General Assembly meeting. They cover the following key areas:

- **Project Management:** Participants are invited to share both positive and critical reflections on project management practices and processes.
- **Current Topics:** This section addresses timely and relevant issues within the project, which may include collaboration infrastructure, satisfaction with project outcomes, or specific Work Package-related matters. Questions related to Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) are included on a recurring basis to raise awareness and encourage engagement with RRI principles across the consortium.
- **Expectations and Perceived Risks:** Participants are asked to provide input on future-oriented aspects, including potential risks and evolving expectations.

A vital component of this process is the collective reflection on survey results within the consortium, preferably during face-to-face meetings. This ensures timely responses to emerging concerns and supports collaborative decision-making—for example, by adjusting agendas or refining processes as needed.

3.5 Risk management

As outlined above, internal surveys and ongoing discussions are used to capture perceived concerns and risks across all consortium partners. Additionally, the regular updates provided by Work Package leaders during the monthly meetings offer a structured opportunity to raise potential risks, report deviations, and propose corrective measures to project management.

The risk management approach adopted in *make-a-thek* follows a structured four-step methodology:

1. **Risk Identification** – Potential risk areas are identified and systematically classified.
2. **Risk Quantification** – The likelihood of each identified risk is assessed, and the potential impact of its occurrence is evaluated.
3. **Risk Response** – Mitigation strategies are developed to reduce or control identified risks, which may include, for example, switching to alternative technologies or approaches.
4. **Risk Control and Reporting** – Risks are continuously monitored, and lessons learned are documented for future reference and improvement.

Risks assessed as having medium to high probability and severe impact receive heightened attention throughout the project lifecycle. Based on the current outlook and the preliminary risk analysis presented in the Description of Action, the project is expected to achieve its objectives successfully.

Routine project risks are managed through standard best practices in project management, drawing on the extensive experience of the consortium partners in delivering successful collaborative projects. Continuous oversight by the project management team and governance bodies ensures that project outcomes are delivered on time and to the expected quality standards.

Description of risk indicated level of (i) likelihood, and (ii) severity: low, medium, high	WP involved	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Shortage of resources for tasks Likelihood: low Severity: high	WP1 & WP2	The project is grounded in detailed budget planning and includes regular monitoring procedures to identify any unforeseen budget or personnel variances at an early stage. An early warning system will be in place to ensure timely detection and response to deviations from the planned resource allocation.

Description of risk indicated level of (i) likelihood, and (ii) severity: low, medium, high	WP involved	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Change in key personnel Likelihood: medium Severity: low	All WPs	Each organisation ensures that multiple team members are familiar with the assigned tasks and deliverables, promoting continuity and reducing dependency on single individuals. Early warning procedures are in place to address potential personnel changes, enabling proactive contingency planning and smooth transitions.
Delay in deliverables causing a knock on effect on related tasks Likelihood: low Severity: high	All WPs	Strict deadline management is maintained, with early warning mechanisms in place to identify potential delays or misalignments. Adequate buffer time is planned between interdependent tasks, key deliverables, and work packages to ensure smooth workflow and timely completion.
3-type of modularity of the <i>make-a-thek</i> approach not applicable to certain libraries Likelihood: low Severity: medium	WP4	A high degree of modularity is built into the project design, which will be addressed through the participatory mapping activities in WP3 (Mapping & Community Activation). If greater flexibility is required, the models will be adapted and extended accordingly to accommodate emerging needs.
Negative reception of training and mentoring; not adequate for target groups Likelihood: low Severity: high	WP5	All materials are co-created in collaboration with stakeholders, ensuring their relevance and resonance. Outputs are reviewed and validated with stakeholder groups to confirm that both tone and content are appropriate and meaningful. Mentoring activities are designed to be flexible and can be tailored to address the specific needs of each pilot.

Description of risk indicated level of (i) likelihood, and (ii) severity: low, medium, high	WP involved	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Dropping out of pilot libraries Likelihood: low Severity: low	WP7	PL2030 benefits from a strong and committed network, with several public libraries having signed letters of commitment. In the event that a partner withdraws, there is a pool of enthusiastic libraries ready and willing to step in and participate.
Low mobilisation of participants for local <i>make-a-thek</i> events Likelihood: low Severity: high	WP6 & WP7	The selected public libraries are well-positioned to engage diverse and wide-ranging audiences. In the event of low participation, we will explore targeted engagement strategies such as small-scale design challenges, prize incentives, and creative concepts to boost interest and attract community involvement.
Missing engagement from under-recognised groups of society Likelihood: medium Severity: medium	WP6 & WP7	Special promotional efforts will be undertaken in collaboration with local representatives of underrepresented groups. Targeted public relations (PR) campaigns will focus on specific communities—including BIPOC, LGBTQIA+, migrants, and people with disabilities—to ensure inclusive outreach. Additionally, the bus will extend its reach to rural areas, promoting broad and equitable access.
Low interest / poor quality from targets in the international pilots Likelihood: low Severity: medium	WP8, WP9 & WP10	Potential candidates have already been identified through the strong international networks of GIG, FRG, and ECA. In the event of a low response rate, the communication campaign will be intensified to broaden outreach and attract additional participants.

Description of risk indicated level of (i) likelihood, and (ii) severity: low, medium, high	WP involved	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Low interest from target groups in the up-take of project outcomes Likelihood: low Severity: medium	WP8, WP9 & WP10	There is demonstrated interest within the partners' extensive networks, supported by a proven track record of impactful, far-reaching communication campaigns. These capabilities will enhance the visibility, reach, and uptake of the project's results. Success stories from the pilot initiatives will be highlighted through funded scaling workshops, further amplifying impact and engagement.

Table 4: make-a-thek critical risks for implementation

Throughout the project, the management team is responsible for closely monitoring overall progress and identifying potential risks. At the same time, risk identification is encouraged as a collaborative effort, integrated into reflective sessions during project meetings. Early communication and open discussion of risks are strongly promoted to foster a shared understanding and enable timely responses. The project management actively supports a culture of openness, where challenges and concerns can be addressed transparently and constructively.

3.6 Visions & Expectations

During the kick-off meeting, the project coordinator facilitated a reflection session aimed at identifying the expectations and long-term visions of all *make-a-thek* project partners. This session was designed to ensure alignment across the consortium, fostering a shared understanding of objectives and mutual awareness of each partner's aspirations for the project. The following two images summarise the collective input in response to two key questions:

- **Expectations** – *What should we achieve during the project?*
- **Vision** – *What legacy do we want to leave in 10 years?*

Picture 4: Visions & Expectations of make-a-thek project partners

3.6.1 Expectations for the *make-a-thek* Project

The *make-a-thek* project envisions a collaborative, inclusive, and inspiring ecosystem that supports circular economy practices within the realms of fashion and craft, anchored in public libraries with makerspaces. Key expectations include:

- **Strong Collaboration & Communication**
Emphasis on mutual collaboration across work packages (WPs), open and honest communication, and clear strategic planning. Partners aim to inspire one another and foster a culture of transparency and shared purpose.
- **Community & Network Building**
A central goal is to transform pilot initiatives into a sustainable network of fashion- and craft-oriented libraries, while also creating connections with craftspersons, makers, and relevant stakeholders at local, national, and international levels, including beyond European borders.
- **Inclusivity & Accessibility**
The project seeks to ensure meaningful participation by embedding inclusivity and accessibility from the outset. This includes developing inclusive pilots, strategies for inclusive spaces, and making content and tools usable for a wide variety of audiences, including those typically underrepresented.
- **Circular Economy & Sustainability**
There is a strong commitment to co-creating positive experiments and

tangible business cases in the regional circular economy. The project will showcase successful pilots, support evidence-based impact, and encourage civic engagement at the local level to promote fairer fashion and sustainable practices.

- **Education & Empowerment**

A key output will be joyful and adaptable learning materials, for online and offline experiences, to inspire makers, designers, and prosumers. The project will serve as a source of inspiration for entrepreneurs and creatives, helping participants transform their passion into sustainable ventures.

- **Visibility & Impact**

The project expects to deliver meaningful internal and external communication, including impactful marketing and storytelling around pilot successes. It will leverage its strong network and communication expertise to expand reach and support long-term adoption of project outcomes.

- **Tools & Resources**

Deliverables such as a modular kit and a publicly accessible repository of circular practices will help ensure that knowledge and tools are widely applicable, scalable, and valuable across different settings and communities.

- **Sustainability & Funding**

Raising additional funding through external partnerships (e.g., local library networks) is seen as a pathway to long-term sustainability and scaling of the initiative after the project funding.

In essence, *make-a-thek* aims to be more than a project: it aspires to be a movement that blends creativity, sustainability, and inclusiveness through hands-on learning, shared knowledge, and community empowerment.

3.6.2 Vision for the *make-a-thek* Project

The long-term vision of *make-a-thek* is to spark a global shift in how communities engage with fashion, crafts, sustainability, and shared spaces—starting with libraries with makerspaces across Europe and extending far beyond.

- **Libraries as Creative Hubs**

In the future, public libraries across Europe, and eventually worldwide, will serve as vibrant spaces for craft, fashion design, co-creation, and repair. They will be equipped with makerspaces and supported by local maker communities, enabling people to do things like repair clothing, learn new skills, and collaborate creatively.

- **A Scalable, Global Movement**

The *make-a-thek* approach aims to evolve into a globally recognized methodology, empowering communities on all continents to reconnect with craft heritage and promote sustainable lifestyles. A strong, cooperative network of locations and communities rooted in public libraries and makerspaces will act as a backbone of this movement.

- **Cultural and Social Transformation**

The project envisions a deep cultural shift: from fast fashion to shared,

communal design; from consumption to creativity; from exclusion to inclusion. Makerspaces and fablabs will act as “third spaces” within urban infrastructure, reflecting the diversity of our communities and providing equal access to tools, knowledge, and opportunities.

- **Empowering People and Stories**

A central part of the vision is that *make-a-thek* participants, especially those from underrepresented backgrounds, will tell their own stories and shape the movement. The project will highlight the **social impact** of action, not just economic success, by fostering inclusive and community-driven innovation.

- **Aligned with Broader European Values**

The initiative contributes to the vision of the **New European Bauhaus**, promoting a greener, more inclusive, and sustainable Europe where arts, culture, and crafts are no longer seen as secondary sectors but as powerful drivers of societal transformation.

- **A New System for a Circular Society**

In ten years, *make-a-thek* envisions its approach integrated into the very fabric of the **15-minute city**, with libraries as key nodes in a circular, community-driven economy. These programs will support sustainable local economies, bio-circular business models, and democratized access to technology and innovation.

- **A Legacy That Continues**

Ultimately, the vision is not only to implement *make-a-thek* successfully but to inspire future projects that build on its foundation, ensuring its legacy and continued evolution.

3.7 Mid-Term SWOT Analysis for *make-a-thek*

A mid-term SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis is planned to take place during a plenary meeting at the midpoint of the *make-a-thek* project. This structured reflection will serve as a strategic checkpoint, allowing the consortium to reassess progress and, if necessary, realign priorities and activities for the second half of the project.

SWOT analysis is a widely used strategic planning tool that helps evaluate internal and external factors influencing a project’s success. It is applicable across various contexts, including policies, programs, projects, organisations, and individual initiatives. In this context:

- **Strengths** and **Weaknesses** are internal factors—attributes inherent to the project team, structure, or resources.
- **Opportunities** and **Threats** are external factors—conditions or trends in the broader environment that may affect the project's performance or outcomes.

This analysis will enable the consortium to identify strategic pathways that:

- Leverage strengths to maximise opportunities (SO strategies),
- Address weaknesses in order to pursue opportunities (WO strategies),
- Use strengths to mitigate potential threats (ST strategies), and
- Minimise both weaknesses and threats through defensive measures (WT strategies).

Guiding Questions for the SWOT Analysis

Strengths (S):

- What are we doing well?
- What assets and unique resources do we have?
- What are our core competencies and Unique Selling Proposition (USP)?
- What do others see as our strengths?

Weaknesses (W):

- Where can we improve?
- What should we avoid?
- Where do we lack critical resources?
- What factors reduce our effectiveness?
- What are perceived externally as our weaknesses?

Opportunities (O):

- What promising opportunities are emerging?
- What political, social, or economic trends could benefit us?
- What new needs of Public Libraries or future users could we meet?

Threats (T):

- What external obstacles do we face?
- Where are we most vulnerable?
- Could any internal weaknesses jeopardise our success?
- What negative trends could impact us?

The outcomes of this mid-term SWOT analysis will feed directly into the strategic planning for the second project phase and ensure the project remains focused, relevant, and resilient in the face of change.

SWOT Matrix	Strengths	Weaknesses
Opportunities	SO-Strategies	WO-Strategies
Threats	ST-Strategies	WT Strategies

Table 5: SWOT Matrix

Once the initial SWOT matrix has been developed based on input from the consortium, the following strategic questions should guide the subsequent discussion and refinement of the project strategy:

- How can *make-a-thek* best leverage its strengths to take advantage of emerging opportunities?
- How can identified weaknesses be minimised by capitalising on available opportunities?
- How can strengths be used to mitigate or reduce the risks associated with external threats?
- How can weaknesses be addressed effectively, even in the presence of anticipated threats?

While the SWOT analysis is a valuable complementary tool for strategic reflection and project adjustment, it is not without limitations. Its structure is inherently linear and often reflects a single perspective—either that of an individual expert or a homogeneous group. To overcome this limitation and enrich the analysis, it is advisable to incorporate external perspectives, such as those from the Advisory Board or key stakeholders, who can offer alternative interpretations and insights into the project's trajectory.

Despite these limitations, SWOT remains a practical and accessible tool for gaining a quick overview of both internal and external project dynamics. As such, it is well-suited to support the *make-a-thek* project's mid-term strategic review.

3.8 Project templates

make-a-thek aims to maintain a consistent project identity through the use of a unified visual and editorial style. This is supported by a set of templates for deliverables, reports, presentations, posters, and other communication and dissemination materials. Additional templates can be developed by the Communication and Outreach team (WP9&10) as needed to support specific project activities.

All available templates are accessible in various formats via the shared project workspace (Google Drive & Basecamp) as well as Canva.

4 Tools and collaboration infrastructure

While the previous section focused on communication and collaboration processes, *make-a-thek* also relies on a range of technical tools to support its collaboration infrastructure. This infrastructure is designed to facilitate effective communication, coordination, and data management across the consortium. The key components include:

- **Project Mailing List:** The central channel for project-wide, asynchronous communication. All team members can be reached via the mailing list: make-a-thek@zsi.at
- **WhatsApp:** Used for quick, ad-hoc communication with the entire team.
- **Zoom:** The platform for regular web conferences, including monthly consortium meetings.
- **Google Drive:** Used for file sharing and collaborative, real-time document editing. This is used for sharing non-sensitive data. Access the shared folder here: [Google Drive Folder](#)
- **Basecamp:** Hosted by PL2030, Basecamp serves as the primary internal project space for secure document exchange and storage—particularly for sensitive or confidential materials, in alignment with the Data Management Plan and GDPR compliance. Access it here: [Basecamp](#)
- **Email and Telephone:** Used for direct, bilateral communication between partners.
- **Project Website:** The public-facing platform for presenting *make-a-thek* activities, outcomes, and updates: <https://www.makeathek.eu/>

This collaboration infrastructure was selected with careful consideration of practical needs, as well as compliance with data privacy and security requirements under the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Sensible/confidential data will be stored only on partners secured servers and will be exchanged with other partners if required by signing the data exchange agreement (see Annex I).

For any new team member to be added to any of the collaboration infrastructure, send an e-mail to kieslinger@zsi.at and fabian@zsi.at and for Basecamp also contact juliette@pl2030.eu

5 Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and societal readiness

5.1 From RRI to societal readiness

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) has been formulated and widely promoted as a guiding principle and policy concept by the European Commission to better align science with society and to meet the so-called grand challenges¹¹. It has been promoted as a cross-cutting issue within the H2020 research programme. Core aspects of RRI relate to how responsible research and innovation should be practiced. This includes elements of **openness and transparency, anticipation and reflection, responsiveness and adaptive change, and diversity and**

¹¹ Health, demographic change and wellbeing; Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research, and the Bioeconomy; Secure, clean and efficient energy; Smart, green and integrated transport; Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials; Europe in a changing world – inclusive, innovative and reflective societies; Secure societies – protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens

inclusion. Ethics, open access, gender and diversity, and public engagement were also core aspects that found their way into European research and innovation programmes as cross-cutting issues and have since been implemented.

Considering RRI as established practice, we now experience a greater focus on the **societal readiness** of research and innovation in Horizon Europe. The concept stresses the necessity of research and innovation to respond closer to the needs and concerns of society. *make-a-thek* has integrated this approach already in the work plan, where WP3 is preparing an evaluation and impact assessment framework that includes societal readiness, which will be implemented throughout the project and assessed in WP11.

Participation is at the heart of both concepts, RRI and societal readiness. And it is also core for the implementation of *make-a-thek* as it leads to strengthening common ownership of the process and its outcomes. Across the work packages in *make-a-thek* co-creation processes will be applied, engaging the concerned actors from the onset in the whole process. Picture 5 below outlines the different levels of participation and while we declare co-creation as the preferred level of participation for the project it is also important to make sure that co-creation is done responsibly and that other levels of participation may be applied in certain contexts and settings.

Schuerz, Stefanie (2023): Levels of Participation in Research and Innovation. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8096864

Picture 5: Levels of participation as defined by ProEthics

There is a vast range of tools and methods with different levels of participation available, e.g. public consultations, public deliberations for decision making, public participation in R&I processes, Citizen Science, etc. The goal of opening up research and innovation processes to the public is to better meet the values, needs, and expectations of society and thus to improve R&I and to find solutions to the so-called grand challenges that society is facing (Cagnin, Amanatidou, & Keenan, 2012).

Co-creation and co-design are regarded as possible empowering methods as they enable participants to shape the development of certain technologies or services and support creative collaboration across stakeholders. *make-a-thek* has a strong commitment to co-creation processes across the various activities and work packages. In particular, in the mapping (WP3), the implementation of the pilots (WP7&8) and community building (WP6) stakeholders will play an active co-creation role. Next to the co-creation of *make-a-thek* activities we will also promote co-creation in the pilots across Europe and beyond.

Participation and coconstruction are both based on the principle of equal partnership across the involved actors. Importantly, we will work along some core principles of participation, such as transparency, participant ownership, openness, reflexivity and flexibility. These values have been defined as **co-evaluation principles** by the coordinating project partner ZSI, who relies on extensive expertise in participatory research (see Picture 6 below).

Picture 6: Principles of co-evaluation (Kieslinger et al. 2022)

5.2 Gender equality, inclusion, and diversity

Gender equality generally means equal rights, opportunities, and responsibilities for all genders so that individuals can exploit and realise their full potentials independently from their sex.

Gender equality as a key dimension of RRI comprises two main aspects (European Commission, 2015), namely to strive for gender-balanced teams in research and innovation (at operational as well as at decision-making level) and the inclusion and integration of gender perspectives in research and innovation content and

process. Gender analysis and gender monitoring throughout the project shall aim at looking at both aspects of gender equality, at the human capital dimension (where possible, apart from institutional conditions), and the research aspect of gender (Föger et al., 2016).

In *make-a-thek* gender is relevant at various levels, when it comes to internal processes, such as the composition of project teams, of work package leaders, of the external experts we choose to work with, the use of gender-sensitive language, the awareness of producing gender-sensitive content, the engagement activities in our pilots, etc. In line with the Toolkit on Gender in EU-funded research (European Commission, 2009) *make-a-thek* will strive at doing gender-sensitive innovation. Particularly in the following project steps gender has to be addressed and taken into account:

- Project design and methodology: we will *make-a-thek* sure that for any of our approaches in co-design and other engagement activities, we will aim at representative data in the sense that different gender perspectives will be described, where relevant.
- Project implementation: Data-collection tools such as questionnaires, interview guidelines, etc. need to be gender-sensitive and use gender-neutral language, and have to allow for differentiation between gender perspectives. In the evaluation data analysis, we will particularly pay attention to whether there are differences across gender, for instance, in terms of artefacts that are produced, in terms of communicating and sharing, etc.
- Dissemination phase – reporting of data: We will use gender-neutral language in our publications. Furthermore, we will sensitively decide which visual materials to use. In addition, we will aim at publishing gender-specific results.

Gender is not regarded as a binary concept in our project, but rather fluid and we aim to explore opportunities for all genders. We are aware of inherent gender and cultural biases and will follow a culturally and gender-sensitive methodology with cultural and gender equality sensitive principles.

Inclusion and Diversity

make-a-thek wants to be beneficial for all and inclusive from the social point of view, creating new opportunities, bringing inspirations, training and business development also for all those population groups generally outside the circuits of innovation. For *make-a-thek*, inclusion also means producing informative and educational content accessible by craftspeople from different sectors and with different levels of knowledge and technical or technological skills, including those without formal education and ancestral training. The mapping, collecting and sharing process of traditional techniques wants to value and preserve the different

traditions and skills, including and embracing socio-cultural diversity as an element of global enrichment.

Especially in our bottom-up co-design approaches we aim to create an environment that reaches new groups, especially vulnerable or historically excluded ones, acknowledging the historical gatekeeping in design and other fields. Our belief is in re-centering historically excluded individuals and underrepresented communities, including those who are BIPOC, LGBTQIA+, migrants, have disabilities, previous experience with the justice system, and others at the intersection of these identities, ensuring their meaningful inclusion in our work. The co-evaluation principles include important guidance on how to assure that the process of participation and co-creation is truly creating equal and meaningful dialogue across stakeholders.

5.3 Ethics

The European Commission defines ethics as a key dimension of RRI as follows:

“European society is based on shared values. In order to adequately respond to societal challenges, research and innovation must respect fundamental rights and the highest ethical standards. Beyond the mandatory legal aspects, this aims to ensure increased societal relevance and acceptability of research and innovation outcomes. Ethics should not be perceived as a constraint to research and innovation, but rather as a way of ensuring high quality results.” (p.4)¹²

Ethics thereby shall not be perceived as a constraint but rather as a guiding principle to help ensure high quality outcomes and to justify decisions. This is also the case for *make-a-thek*. While there is no specific work package dedicated to legal and ethical aspects we are very cautious and the management team is guiding the consortium on conducting ethically sound innovation. We will deal with the three main aspects of ethics as defined by the European Commission (2015), namely 1) Research integrity and good research practice, 2) Research ethics for the protection of research objects, and 3) Societal relevance and ethical acceptability of research and innovation outcomes.

Ethics further implies social justice and inclusion aspects: The widest range of societal actors and civil society shall benefit from research and innovation outcomes. In other words, products and services as a result of Research & Innovation (R&I) activities shall be acceptable and affordable for different social groups, which is also a special goal of *make-a-thek* and its focus on inclusion and diversity.

Ethics is an integral part of responsible research, from the conceptual phase to the publication of research results. The consortium of *make-a-thek* is clearly committed to showing appreciation of potential ethical issues that may arise during the course of the project and has as such defined a set of procedures on how to deal with ethics in a responsible way.

¹²

http://ec.europa.eu/research/science-society/document_library/pdf_06/responsible-research-and-innovation-leaflet_en.pdf

The main aspects the project is dealing with in regards to ethics are the protection of identity, privacy, obtaining informed consent, and communicating benefits and risks to the involved target groups. The activities performed in *make-a-thek* may include data collection from individuals and organisations remotely as well as on-site. In the following, we outline the basic processes of ethical compliance of the project with a general view on the scientific data collection.

Data protection and privacy

During any data collection process, data protection issues with regards to handling personal data will be addressed by the following strategies:

Participants, who volunteer to be enrolled in our activities, will be exhaustively informed so that they are able to autonomously decide whether they consent to participate or not. The purposes of the research, the procedures as well as the handling of their data (protection, storage) will be explained. For online interviews, these explanations will be a part of the initial briefing of interviewees. For face-to-face interventions, informed consent (provided in the Data Management Plan) shall be agreed upon and signed by both the study participants as well as the respective research partner.

The data exploitation will be in line with the respective national data protection acts. Since data privacy is under threat when data is traced back to individuals – they may become identifiable and the data may be abused – to mitigate this risk, we will anonymise all data. In addition, we may be dealing with data coming from traditional knowledge, such as from indigenous people. In order to ensure their fair participation through Community-based research techniques we will take advantage of the UN declaration on indigenous people, the Nagoya protocol, and related resources.

Data gathered through questionnaires, interviews, observational studies, focus groups, workshops, and other possible data gathering methods during this research will be anonymised and therefore the data cannot be traced back to the individual. Data will be stored only in anonymous forms so the identities of the participants will only be known by the research partners involved. Raw data like interview protocols and audio files will be shared within the consortium partners only after having signed the confidentiality agreement (See Annex I). Reports based on interviews, focus groups and other data gathering methods will be based on aggregated information and will comprise anonymous quotations respectively.

The collected data will be stored on password-protected servers at the partner institution responsible for data collection and analysis. The data will be used only within the project and will not be made accessible for any third party, unless anonymised. Sensitive data or personal data will not be stored after the end of the project (incl. the time for final publications) unless required by specific national legislation.

The stored data do not contain the names or addresses of participants and will be edited for full anonymity before being processed (e.g. in project reports).

Communication strategy

Study participants will be made aware of the potential benefits and identified risks of participating in the project at all times.

The main means of communicating benefits and risks to the individual is the informed consent (see Data Management Plan). Prior to consent, each individual participant in any of the studies in *make-a-thek* will be clearly informed of its goals, its possible adverse events, and the possibility to refuse to enter or to retract at any time with no consequences. This will be done through a project information sheet or the informed consent form and it will be reinforced verbally.

In order to *make-a-thek* sure that participants are able to recall what they agree upon when signing, the informed consent forms will be provided in the native language of the participants. In addition, the consortium partners will *make-a-thek* sure that the informed consent is written in a language suitable for the target group(s). Different informed consents will be made available, e.g. consent of adult participants, parental consent, informed assent for children/minors.

For media material (e.g. photos, videos) produced during any of the *make-a-thek* events, a **media waiver** will be distributed to participants to *make-a-thek* sure that participants are aware of this and agree/disagree with the production and use of such material by the project partners. A template for the waiver is provided in Annex IV of this document.

Informed consent/informed assent

As stated above informed consent/assent will be collected from all participants involved in *make-a-thek* studies. The declaration of consent forms is provided in the Data Management Plan (DMP).

Relevant regulations and scientific standards

The consortium is following European regulations and scientific standards to perform ethical research. The following lists some of the basic regulations and guidelines.

The *make-a-thek* project will fully respect the citizens' rights as reported by EGE and as proclaimed in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (2000/C 364/01), having as its main goal to enhance and to foster the participation of European citizens to education, regardless of cultural, linguistic or social backgrounds. Regarding the personal data collected during the research, the

project will *make-a-thek* every effort to heed the rules for the protection of personal data as described in Directive 95/46/EC¹³.

In addition, the consortium is following the following European Regulations and Guidelines:

- The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union:
<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:12012P/TXT>
- European Convention on Human Rights
http://www.echr.coe.int/Documents/Convention_ENG.pdf
- Horizon 2020 ethics self-assessment
http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/doc/call/h2020/h2020-m-sca-itn-2015/1620147-h2020_-_guidance_ethics_self_assess_en.pdf
- EU Code of Conduct:
[https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32018D0221\(02\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32018D0221(02))
- European Textbook on Ethics in Research
https://ec.europa.eu/research/science-society/document_library/pdf_06/textbook-on-ethics-report_en.pdf
- European data protection legislation
- RESPECT Code of Practice for Socio-Economic Research
- Code of Ethics of the International Sociological Association (ISA)

National and Local Regulations and Standards

In addition to the more general and EU-wide guidelines, project partners have to adhere to, and respect, national regulations, and laws as well as to research organisational ethical approval as requested by their own institutions. All partners are aware of their responsibilities in that respect and will follow the respective guidelines. It should be stressed that many partners are located outside the European Union and additional national regulations may apply.

More details about data handling will be available in the Data Management Plan.

6 Open access and open research data

The project firmly believes in openness to be a major factor for innovation and this was also one of the main motivations for *make-a-thek*, which promotes open access to sustainable fashion, crafts and heritage practices in public libraries. Openness has many facets. The most important ones for the *make-a-thek* consortium are:

¹³ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=URISERV%3A114012>

- **Open project collaboration.** All partners are committed to developing (working) relationships with external partners for mutual benefit. Making contacts with similar projects and establishing collaboration is considered beneficial for all. Open collaboration in *make-a-thek* is understood in a trans-disciplinary way, opening innovation processes to the wider public and allowing a new form of collaboration as intended in the co-design activities of the project.
- **Open source technology.** From a technology perspective, the project fosters the sharing of any *make-a-thek* infrastructure, tools or software. A main aim is to share the co-designed technological artefacts with the community. Business models and exploitation strategies are not based on locking down access to project results, but on providing added value through services.
- **Open access to scientific results.** From a scientific perspective, the consortium clearly favours open access to its scientific output, which is supported by several project members' internal policies of supporting open access in general.
- **Open access to research data.** *make-a-thek* is committed to providing access not only to project results and processes, but also to data collected during that process. Although *make-a-thek* is an innovation action according to the work programme definition and not a research action, some research related data will be collected, mainly from an evaluation perspective. Although the general policy of the *make-a-thek* project is to apply "open by default" to its research data, we have to handle privacy issues with special care. Legal rules on anonymity, as described above, are thus highly relevant and need to be agreed upon with each of the participants. In case of doubt, data privacy of our participants always prevails over open data policy.

make-a-thek adheres to these principles of openness and we encourage our partners and participants to do the same in order to "extend the responsibility" especially for the uptake beyond *make-a-thek*. The project's data handling will be described in the Data Management Plan. The open access strategy will be detailed in the following sections.

6.1 Open access strategy for publications and other artifacts

In line with the EC policy initiative on open access¹⁴, which refers to the practice of granting free Internet access to research articles, the project is committed to following a publication strategy considering a mix of both 'Green open access' (immediate or delayed open access that is provided through self-archiving) and 'Gold open access' (immediate open access that is provided by a publisher) as far as possible.

¹⁴<http://ec.europa.eu/research/science-society/index.cfm?fuseaction=public.topic&id=1294&lang=1>

All deliverables labelled as “public” will be made accessible via the *make-a-thek* website. The publications stemming from the project work will also be made available on the website as far as it does not infringe the publishers’ rights as well as on the Zenodo platform.

All outcomes of the project, including design, protocols, databases, etc. that are labelled as “public” will be distributed under a specific free/open license, where the authors retain the authors’ rights but the users can redistribute the content freely. The following are a few relevant sources for deciding on the specific license for each outcome:

- **Data:**
 - A definition of Open Data:
 - Licenses:
- **Software:**
 - Free Software
 - The definition:
 - Licenses:
 - Open Source Software:
 - The definition:
 - Licenses:
- **Reports, publications, media:**
 - Creative Commons
 - Explanation:
 - Licenses:
 - Choose a license:
 - Sharing publications on the project website and via Zenodo

To summarise, the main open access points for *make-a-thek* data, publications, and innovation are:

- The project website: <https://www.makeathek.eu/>
- Zenodo: for depositing publications (<https://zenodo.org/>)
- OpenAIRE for depositing research data (<https://www.openaire.eu/>)
- Github/Gitlab (<https://github.com/>)

6.2 Open access and open data handling process

The internal procedures to grant open access to any publication, research data, or other innovation stemming from the *make-a-thek* project (e.g. technology), are following a lightweight structure, while respecting ethical issues at all times.

The main workflow starts at the WP level, where each team is responsible for respecting ethical procedures at all times during the data gathering and processing steps. The WP/working team members are also responsible for any data anonymization, if applicable. An agreement has to be reached within the team for making any outcome openly available; the final approval is done by the Work Package Leader Group. Due to the nature of the project, the Data Management Plan may have to be revised during the course of project activities. As the co-design approach is a rather dynamic methodology it is not possible to clearly specify all data sources and collected outcomes from the beginning.

More details on all aspects related to data handling are provided in the Deliverable D1.2 Data Management Plan, which is due in Month 6.

7 Conclusions

This handbook outlines the core procedures guiding the *make-a-thek* project to ensure effective implementation and the achievement of high-quality results, in alignment with the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). Key elements of the European RRI framework—such as open access, ethical standards, and the engagement of diverse societal actors—are central to the project's approach (European Union, 2012). *make-a-thek* is firmly committed to addressing societal challenges responsibly, both through its objectives and the way in which project activities are carried out.

Although presented as a formal report and deliverable, this handbook is intended as a living document—subject to updates, revisions, and critical reflection by the consortium throughout the project lifecycle. The processes and protocols described herein are integrated into the consortium's day-to-day operations. Supporting materials (e.g. informed consent templates, the data management plan) are available through the project's collaboration platforms, including **Google Drive** and **Basecamp**.

Any significant updates to the handbook, along with outcomes from key strategic tools such as the SWOT analysis or additional quality assurance measures, will be documented in the project's regular management reports.

8 References

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9 Annex I – Confidentiality Agreement and Data Exchange Format

Confidentiality Agreement

Research data shared between the researchers in the *make-a-thek* project may contain **personal identifiable information (PII)**, the usage of which is protected by law. To comply with this law, usage, and sharing of data is restricted and it is essential that you follow the rules and guidelines described in the ethical guidelines defined for *make-a-thek* for collecting, processing, sharing, and storage of data.

In addition to this you are obliged to comply with the following terms:

- I will not share the participant data, collected by the project team, in which I am in receipt with any third parties, including the case study organisations, employers of the participants, or other members of the consortium of the *make-a-thek* project without explicit, written consent from the person(s) who provided the data.
- Where relevant, I will instruct the people for whom I have responsibility who have access to the data of the relevant ethical protocols and ensure that they follow the guidelines defined for the project, as listed below.
- I will delete the data at least _____ months after the project outcomes have been published (recommended time is 3 months).

Declaration: I hereby declare my consent with the rules outlined above:

Date:

Name & Organisation:

Signature:

List of persons in my organisation who have access to the data:

Organisation	Name of person

Data Exchange Form

As consortium partners in the *make-a-thek* consortium, we agree to share **personal identifiable information (PII)** of individuals and/or organisations as defined in the Confidentiality Agreement.

This data exchange form regulates the exchange between partners regarding sensitive data.

Description	Name of person
Researcher(s) responsible for the data (who collected the data originally)	
Type of data (e.g. interview recording, questionnaire, etc.)	
Sensitivity of data (describe briefly why this specific data is highly sensible)	
Consent form signed by all involved participants	
Storage location	
Person(s) who have access to the data	
Purpose of sharing	
Confidentiality agreement signed	
Data retention (timeframe for storing the shared data)	

Date:

Name & Organisation:

Signature:

10 Annex II – Checklist for Deliverables

1. Overall technical evaluation of the deliverable

- Does the deliverable contain new, or value added information?
- Are there any major technical errors, omissions, lack of necessary details?
- How do the results compare with the state of the art and/or parallel activities?
- What value does the document add to the project partners?

2. Executive summary

- Are the following questions clearly asked and answered?
 - Which problem(s) and key questions of interest to intended readers are addressed?
 - What are the expected main benefits of this deliverable?
 - What are the results contained in this deliverable?
 - Who are the main consumers for this deliverable, e.g. who should read it?
 - Why should I read the deliverable?
 - Suggestions/recommendations for follow-up actions by project participants and/or by the general public.
- Is the length acceptable for the executive summary (e.g. approx. 2 pages)?

3. Introduction

- Is the purpose of the document clearly stated?
- Is the technical subject properly introduced?
- If necessary, is there a guide to the reader (document structure, short description of chapters and relationships)?
- If necessary, are there statements on technical assumption, readers' prerequisites, relationships with other documents or parallel activities?

4. The main part of the deliverable

- Does it contain what was defined in the deliverable description in the DoA?
- If something has been left out, have clear and valid reasons been given as to why?
- Is the key part structured in a logical way?
- Is the content appropriate for the intended audience? Does it only include essential information?
- Does it duplicate or contradict standards or other on-going known initiatives? If yes, the affected standard or initiatives need to be identified.
- Is the length acceptable (approx. 30 pages for main part)?

5. Conclusion

- Are conclusions reached? Are they within the consortium perspective?
- Are any necessary follow-up actions clearly indicated?
- Are the conclusions consistent with the executive summary?
- Should this Deliverable be
 - Utilised by other projects?
 - Released (in full or part) to the Associated Partner Network or to PES initiatives such as PES-to-PES dialogue?

6. Annexes (optional)

- Are they complete in all parts?
- Relevant for the content described in the deliverable?

11 Annex III Peer Review Template

Instructions:

Peer reviewers should fill out all six sections in this template and send the completed template to the editor/main author on or before the specified due date.

1. Basic Information

- Deliverable Nr & Title:
- Main Author/Editor:
- Peer Reviewer (Institution, Person):
- Date of Receipt of Deliverable:
- Date of Sending out the completed peer review:

2. Length of the deliverable

- Is the length of the deliverable justified? – YES - NO
- If no, please specify by e.g. indicating parts that are superfluous, irrelevant, redundant, unspecific or would need more explanation?

3. Content

- Does the deliverable meet the objectives of the deliverable described in the respective Work Package Work Description? – YES - NO
 - If not, please indicate the parts where improvement is necessary.
- Is the content of the deliverable focused and presented in a precise and to-the-point manner? – YES - NO
 - If not, please indicate the parts where improvement is necessary.
- Does the deliverable require substantial revision or rewriting? – YES - NO
 - If yes, please give concrete suggestions how to improve the deliverable.

4. Major strengths

5. Major weaknesses

6. Review Summary

The current version of the deliverable is []:

- 1: applicable and ready to be submitted to the EC, if required;
- 2: applicable, but requires minor revisions;
- 3: inapplicable and requires substantial revisions.

Is it necessary for the revised deliverables to be reviewed again before submitting it to the EC (1:Yes, 2: No)? []

Other remarks:

12 Annex IV Consent from for image processing

The _____¹⁵ is the Controller of the personal data of the interested party and hereby informs you that this data will be processed in accordance with the provisions of *Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of 27 April 2016 (GDPR)*, and *Spanish Law 1/1982 on Civil Protection of the Right to Honour, Personal and Family Intimacy and Own Image*¹⁶; therefore, you are provided with the following information on processing:

Purposes of the processing: Recording still images and videos of the activities carried out by the Controller to [advertise the activities on the media], with the Interested Party's consent.

Data Storage Criteria: Data will be stored while there is a mutual interest in the purpose of the processing, and when it is no longer necessary for this purpose, it will be deleted using appropriate security measures to guarantee their pseudonymisation or total destruction.

Data Sharing: The Interested Party may agree to or refuse processing by marking the corresponding box with an X, YES (I give my consent) or NO (I do not give my consent) for the following categories of recipients:

YES	NO	AUTHORISATION TO SHARE DATA
X		Recording of images and videos of the interested party during the activities of the European <i>make-a-thek</i> project (contract #101177660).
X		Publication of images and videos in the media of the Controller and its associated projects <i>make-a-thek</i> .
X		Publication of images and videos in media external to the Controller for the promotion and dissemination of activities, projects and initiatives of the Controller.

Rights of the interested party:

- The right to withdraw consent at any time.
- The rights of access, rectification, portability and removal of data and limitation or opposition to processing.

¹⁵ insert name of organisation

¹⁶ insert national law in the respective country or delete in case of a distributed event

